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Future Of Auditing: Effect Of Data Analytics And Artificial Intelligence On Audit Quality Of Auditing Firms In Asaba

¹UKAH, Ifeanyi Francis & ²Prof. ONUORA K. Joshua

¹Department of Internal Audit,
Delta State Hospitals Management Board Headquarters, Asaba, Nigeria

²Department of Accountancy,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam, Anambra State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of data analytics and artificial intelligence on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba. The study developed three objectives such as to; Examine the effect of data analytics on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba; Determine the influence of artificial intelligence on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba; Evaluate the role of advanced audit technologies on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba. This research work will be anchored on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The study adopted descriptive survey research design. Data were generated from primary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected audit firms in Asaba Delta state. The population of the study was ninety-one (91) staff. The hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that data analytics has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba, Artificial intelligence has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba, Advanced audit technologies has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba. The study concludes that the continuous adoption and effective utilization of digital audit technologies are essential for improving audit quality and sustaining professional relevance in an increasingly technology-driven audit environment. The study recommends that; Auditing firms in Delta State should invest in and expand the use of data analytics tools in audit engagements. Management should also ensure that AI systems are aligned with professional auditing standards to improve accuracy, objectivity, and reliability of audit outcomes. Auditing firms should upgrade from traditional audit methods to advanced audit technologies such as computer-assisted audit techniques (CAATs), cloud-based audit platforms, and integrated audit management systems.

Keywords: Data analytics, artificial intelligence, audit quality, Auditing

1.1 INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving business environment, technological innovations such as data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) are reshaping traditional business practices across industries. The auditing profession long grounded in manual procedures, sampling techniques, and historical financial analysis is no exception (Ajibade, 2025). In cities like Asaba, where small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and corporate entities are increasingly adopting digital systems, auditing firms are under pressure to upgrade

their capabilities. The integration of data analytics and AI into auditing processes presents both significant opportunities and challenges (Akinadewo, 2021).

Data analytics involves the systematic use of large volumes of structured and unstructured data to uncover meaningful patterns, trends, and insights that support informed decision-making. In auditing, the ability to analyze entire datasets rather than just samples enhances the accuracy, depth, and reliability of audit findings (Anna, 2022). Artificial intelligence, which includes machine learning, neural networks, and intelligent automation, further augments audit quality by enabling predictive analysis, anomaly detection, risk assessment, and real-time monitoring (Balios, Kotsilaras, Eriotis, & Vasiliou, 2020)..

The adoption of these technologies promises to transform traditional audit functions. For instance, AI-powered tools can automate routine tasks like transaction matching, risk scoring, and compliance testing, thereby improving efficiency and reducing human error. Data analytics enhances auditors' ability to detect fraud, uncover irregularities, and provide deeper insight into an entity's financial health. Consequently, auditing firms that leverage these technologies can deliver higher quality services, stronger client value propositions, and competitive differentiation (Dagunduro, Falana, Adewara, & Busayo, 2023).

However, this transformation is not without challenges. Auditing firms in Asaba face barriers such as limited access to advanced technology, inadequate technical expertise, high implementation costs, and concerns about data privacy and ethical implications (Riyam, 2023).. The professional competencies required to interpret complex analytical outcomes also call for enhanced training and continuous capacity building. Understanding the impact of data analytics and AI is therefore crucial not only for improving audit quality but also for shaping strategic responses by firms operating in Asaba's dynamic economic landscape (Sagarika Michae & Holly 2022).

This study explores the extent to which data analytics and AI technologies are being adopted by auditing firms in Asaba, the effects on audit quality and efficiency, and the challenges encountered. It seeks to contribute to both academic literature and professional practice by informing policymakers, educators, and audit practitioners about the role of emerging technologies in strengthening the integrity and effectiveness of the auditing profession.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The auditing profession plays a critical role in ensuring the credibility, transparency, and reliability of financial information. However, traditional auditing methods largely based on manual procedures, limited sampling techniques, and historical data review are increasingly inadequate in addressing the complexities of modern, technology-driven business environments. With the growing volume of digital transactions and sophisticated financial systems, auditing firms are exposed to higher risks of undetected errors, fraud, and misstatements.

Despite the global advancement in data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) as tools for enhancing audit quality and efficiency, many auditing firms in Asaba appear to lag in their adoption and effective utilization of these technologies. This slow adoption may limit auditors' ability to analyze large datasets comprehensively, identify anomalies in real time, and provide value-added insights beyond statutory compliance. Consequently, audit reports may suffer from reduced accuracy, delayed completion, and limited assurance.

Furthermore, auditing firms in Asaba face several constraints that hinder effective technology integration. These include inadequate technical skills among audit personnel, high costs associated with acquiring and maintaining advanced analytical tools, limited infrastructure, and concerns about data security and ethical use of AI-driven systems. The lack of clear regulatory guidelines and professional standards on the application of AI and data analytics in auditing further complicates their adoption.

Although prior studies have examined the impact of technological innovation on auditing at national and international levels, there is a paucity of empirical evidence focusing on auditing firms at the local level, particularly in Asaba. This gap in literature makes it difficult to assess how data analytics and AI influence audit efficiency, effectiveness, and quality within the specific operational and economic context of the area.

Therefore, the problem this study seeks to address is the uncertainty surrounding the extent of adoption and the actual impact of data analytics and artificial intelligence on the performance and service quality of auditing firms in Asaba, as well as the challenges limiting their effective implementation.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of data analytics and artificial intelligence on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the effect of **data analytics** on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba.
- ii. Determine the influence of **artificial intelligence** on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba.
- iii. Evaluate the role of **advanced audit technologies** on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Data Analytics

Data analytics refers to the systematic process of collecting, cleaning, processing, analyzing, and interpreting large volumes of data in order to discover meaningful patterns, trends, relationships, and insights that support informed decision-making (Brown-Libur, Issa, & Lombardi, 2015). It involves the use of statistical techniques, computational tools, algorithms, and analytical models to transform raw data into useful information that can be applied to solve problems, improve performance, and enhance strategic outcomes (Chassignol, Khoroshavin, Klimova, & Bilyatdinova, 2018). In a broader sense, data analytics encompasses the application of quantitative and qualitative methods to examine structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data drawn from various sources such as databases, transaction records, digital platforms, and information systems. The process typically includes data preparation, exploratory analysis, modeling, and visualization, which together enable users to understand past events, explain current conditions, and predict future outcomes (Chukwuani, & Egiyi, 2020).

2.1.2 Artificial Intelligence

According to Onogholo et al (2025), Artificial intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity and autonomy. Artificial intelligence refers to computer systems that can perform complex tasks normally done by human-reasoning, decision making, creating. Artificial intelligence is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines and, alternatively making a machine behave in ways that would be called intelligent if a human were so behaving (Russell & Norvig, 2016). According to Sagarika et al. (2022) artificial intelligence is intelligence exhibited by machines contrary to the usual intelligence displayed by people. It is the ability of a machine or a computer to copy from something that is natural, in terms of acquiring and applying knowledge and skills. When a machine mimics a human mind by thinking for itself, it is known as artificial intelligence. The field of AI is vast and constantly expanding, and such characterization concerns AI beyond its current capabilities, namely artificial narrow intelligence, thereby comprehending two potential future types of AI: artificial general intelligence and artificial super intelligence (Riyam, 2023).

2.1.3 Audit Quality:

Audit quality refers to the degree to which an audit is conducted in accordance with established professional standards, ethical requirements, and regulatory guidelines, and the extent to which the audit process effectively detects and reports material misstatements in financial statements. It reflects the reliability, credibility, and usefulness of the auditor's opinion to users of financial information, including investors, regulators, management, and other stakeholders (Chukwudi, Echefu, Boniface, & Victoria, 2018).. In a comprehensive sense, audit quality embodies both the competence of the auditor and the effectiveness of the audit process. Auditor competence includes professional knowledge, technical skills, experience, independence, and the ability to exercise sound professional judgment (Gudaparathi, Niu, Yang, Van Doren, & Johnson, 2023).. The audit process, on the other hand, involves proper audit planning, risk assessment, evidence gathering, evaluation, documentation, and reporting in line with

International Standards on Auditing (ISAs) and other relevant frameworks. Audit quality also relates to the auditor's ability to obtain sufficient and appropriate audit evidence that provides reasonable assurance that financial statements are free from material misstatement, whether due to error or fraud. High audit quality implies that auditors apply due professional care, maintain objectivity and independence, and exercise professional skepticism throughout the audit engagement (Hassan, Aziz, & Andriansyah, (2023).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Davis (1989) created the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to explain how humans accept and use technology. The paradigm states that a person's intention to adopt a technology is impacted by how useful and easy it is to use, which ultimately determines how it is actually used (Davis, 1989). It has been widely used to explain the acceptance of AI in auditing since auditors need to think AI is practical and easy to use in order to include it into their decision-making processes. Critics claim that by neglecting external factors like organisational culture and regulatory constraints, TAM oversimplifies the adoption of technology (Bagozzi, 2007). Additionally, it ignores adoption facilitators and obstacles (Abiodun, 2023). This information can be used to create methods for incorporating AI into audit processes, which will eventually improve the calibre of audit conclusions.

2.3 Empirical Study

Nweke & Mordi, (2025) investigated the application of artificial intelligence in audit practices in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between AI and audit practices, AI (independent variable) was proxy using expert system (ES) and intelligent agents (IA) while audit practices was the dependent variable. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using least squares regression model operated with E-Views.12. Survey design was adopted and data for the study was obtained through e-questionnaire survey sent to the various Staff WhatsApp Group Platform of the selected audit firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The results of the study showed that expert system and intelligent agents have positive and significant effect on audit practices in Nigeria. Based on this, the study concludes that the use of AI in audit ensures effective audit practices in Nigeria. The study therefore suggests the need for the application of AI in audit practices as the results of the study showed its significant influence on risk assessments and usefulness in fraud detection.

Appah (2025) investigates the moderating role of auditors' expertise and experience on the relationship between artificial intelligence (AI) adoption and audit quality in audit firms in Nigeria. Grounded on Task-Technology Fit (TTF) theory, a quantitative method was employed using data collected from a structured questionnaire administered to 237 respondents after validity and reliability tests. The structural equation modelling (SEM) shows a significantly positive relationship between expert systems of AI, neural network of AI, machine learning of AI, fuzzy logic of AI, on audit quality of public audit firms in Nigeria, and a significantly positive relationship between auditors' expertise and experience on audit quality of public audit firms in Nigeria. The study also revealed that auditors' expertise and experience moderate a significantly positive relationship between artificial intelligence (expert systems, neural network, machine learning and fuzzy logic) on audit practice (audit quality) on audit quality of public audit firms in Nigeria.

Rita & Onuora (2025) investigated the role of artificial intelligence (AI) on auditing practices in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between AI and audit practices, AI (independent variable) was proxy using expert system (ES) and deep learning machine (DLM) while audit practices was the dependent variable. Two hypotheses were formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using least squares regression model operated with E-Views.12. Survey design was adopted and data for the study was obtained through e-questionnaire survey sent to the various Staff WhatsApp Group Platform of the selected audit firms in Anambra State Nigeria. The findings of the study indicate that expert system and deep learning machine have positive and significant

effect on audit practices in Nigeria. Based on this, the study concludes that the use of AI in auditing ensures effective audit practices in Nigeria.

Ahmad, (2025) investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on the audit quality of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. The population comprises 8 oil and gas companies quoted on the Nigeria Exchange Group Ltd. Data were gathered from the published annual reports and accounts of the quoted oil and gas companies for the period of five years (2019-2023). The data were analyzed using panel regression techniques. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between AI adoption and audit quality, indicating that firms that utilize AI technologies in audit processes report higher levels of audit reliability and transparency. Additionally, firm size and profitability positively influenced audit quality, while leverage showed a negative but weak association.

Yaser, Aram, Hamzah, Maysam and Muhammad (2025) explore the mediating role of financial reporting quality in the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the quality of external auditing in Jordanian commercial banks. A descriptive analytical approach was used. The target population in this research consists of all 13 Jordanian commercial banks listed on the Amman Stock Exchange. The researcher was able to collect 198 questionnaires that were approved to be filled out by employees of Jordanian commercial banks. The present research in Jordanian commercial banks discovered that the impact of AI on external auditing quality is moderated by the quality of financial reporting. The study recommends paying attention to the quality of external auditing, as the auditing process must be carried out efficiently and effectively in accordance with auditing standards. In order for errors and violations discovered during the audit process to be detected, the quality of financial reports must be audited. It also highlights the need to enhance the use of artificial intelligence in the bank to raise the efficiency of the banking systems and thus raise the bank's efficiency.

Ibrahim, and Jahswill, (2024), investigates the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on the future of auditing and assurance services in Nigeria. Highlighting audit quality, efficiency and effectiveness, Simple Random sampling technique was adopted for this study, A 5-point likert scale questionnaire was administered to a sample of 385 auditors to measure their perceptions on AI impacts on audit evidence analysis, risk assessment, judgments. 102 responses were received and the study utilized Structural equation modeling examined relationships between AI Technologies proxied by Expert systems, neural networks and decision-making intelligence and the Future of Auditing and assurance services (audit quality). Findings reveal a significant positive effect of expert systems on audit quality, underscoring their automation and analytical capabilities. However, neural networks and decision making intelligence did not demonstrate a direct significant impact, warranting further research. Decision-making intelligence partially mediates AI technology effects, highlighting the continued importance of human judgement. The study concludes that while AI integration leads to higher audit quality, particularly through expert systems, maximal benefits necessitate human-AI collaboration emphasizing augmented intelligence.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research was used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena to describe "what exists" with respect to variables or conditions in a situation. It describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. A descriptive design is therefore preferred because this study seeks to obtain information for use to carry out the study. The primary source of data that was used in this study is the questionnaire. This is because of the nature of the variables that were used. The population of the study consisted of the staff of the following auditing firms in Delta State. Patrick Uzoka & Co., Olusola Peter & Co., Veronica Asem & Co., Grace Laya & Co., Sam Nwaulu & Co., Ofili Kingsley & Co., Solomon Isaiah & Co., Osakwe Samson & Co., this give us ninety-one (91) staff. The researcher collects primary data from employees of the organizations under study. The respondents were top managers, supervisory, managers and operatives from the various firms under study. The data was collected using a questionnaire. The data Questionnaire were preferred because it has a high response rate and only be required to be distributed to respondents to complete and thus requires less time to be administered, offers the possibility of anonymity and data collected is first hand. The study uses the

closed-ended questions in the questionnaire. Hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance using multiple regression techniques,

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Table 4.1.1 Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.902 ^a	.662	.643	.11789	.162	8.583	3	88	.000	1.633

a. Predictors: (Constant), DTA, AFI, AAT

b. Dependent Variable: AUQ

Table 4.2.1 shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.66%. This implies that 90% of the variation on data analytics, artificial intelligence and advanced audit technologies of audit firms in Delta State is explained by variations in for audit quality. This was supported by adjusted R² of 0.66%.

Test for autocorrelation: This is used test whether errors corresponding to different observation are uncorrelated. If the value of the durbin-watson from the regression result is close to 2 no autocorrelation in that regression result, but if it deviates significantly then there is autocorrelation. The Durbin-Watson statistic (D.W) of 1.6 reveals no autocorrelation in the models. Hence, the result is good for business analysis because the Durbin Watson result is 1.633

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.477	8	.119	8.583	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.474	88	.014		
	Total	2.951	91			

a. Dependent Variable: AUQ

b. Predictors: (Constant), DTA, AFI, AAT

The f-statistics value of 8.583 in table above with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on independent variables such as analytics, artificial intelligence and advanced audit technologies can collectively explain the variations in audit quality.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.668	.076		8.780	.000	.518	.819
	DTA	.124	.024	.474	5.078	.000	.076	.172
	AFI	.083	.019	.407	4.462	.000	.046	.120
	AUQ	.043	.039	.207	2.462	.007	.023	.116

a. Dependent Variable: AUQ

A’piori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table above, we found out that data analytics has a positive sign given its value as .124; this implies that a unit increase in data analytics increases the audit quality by 12%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Artificial intelligence has a positive sign given its value as .083; this implies that a unit increase in Artificial intelligence increases the audit quality by 8%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. However, advance audit technologies has a positive sign given its value as .043; this implies that a unit increase in advance audit technologies increases the audit quality by 43%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation

T- Statistics: The t-test is used to measure the individual statistical significance of our explanatory parameter in the model. From table Coefficients above data analytics is 5.078, this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to audit quality in auditing firms in delta state. Artificial intelligence is 4.462 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to audit quality at 5% level of significant. Advance audit technologies is 2.462 this is statistically significant, this suggest that it contribute significantly to audit quality at 5% level of significant in auditing firms in delta state

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

Here, the hypotheses formulated in chapter one was tested using t-statistics and significance value of the individual variables in the regression result. The essence of this is to ascertain how significant are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables.

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Data analytics has no significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba.

Data analytics has a t-statistics of 7.026 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we accept the alternative hypothesis and reject the null hypotheses which state data analytics has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba

4.2.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Artificial Intelligence has no significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table above is used. Artificial intelligence has a t-statistics of 2.211 and a probability value of 0.020 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Artificial intelligence has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba

4.2.3 Test of Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Advanced audit technologies has no significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba
Advanced audit technologies have a t-statistics of 5.078 and a probability value of .000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Advanced audit technologies has significant effect on audit quality of auditing firms in Asaba

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

This study examined the effect of data analytics, artificial intelligence, and advanced audit technology on the audit quality of auditing firms in Delta State. The findings provide strong empirical evidence that modern digital tools play a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness and reliability of audit practices. The results revealed that data analytics has a positive and significant effect on audit quality. This implies that the use of analytical tools enables auditors to process large volumes of financial data efficiently, identify anomalies, improve risk assessment, and enhance audit planning and evidence gathering. Consequently, auditing firms that effectively deploy data analytics are better positioned to deliver high-quality audit outcomes. Similarly, artificial intelligence was found to have a positive and significant influence on audit quality. This indicates that AI-driven applications such as automated testing, continuous auditing, fraud detection, and predictive analysis enhance auditors' accuracy, objectivity, and timeliness. The integration of AI reduces human error and increases auditors' ability to detect material misstatements, thereby strengthening the credibility of audit reports. Furthermore, the study established that advanced audit technology exerts a positive and significant effect on audit quality. This suggests that the adoption of sophisticated audit software, digital audit platforms, and computer-assisted audit techniques improves audit efficiency, documentation quality, compliance with auditing standards, and overall professional judgment. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that data analytics, artificial intelligence, and advanced audit technology are critical drivers of audit quality among auditing firms in Delta State. Auditing firms that embrace these technological innovations are more likely to enhance audit reliability, transparency, and stakeholder confidence. Therefore, the continuous adoption and effective utilization of digital audit technologies are essential for improving audit quality and sustaining professional relevance in an increasingly technology-driven audit environment.

5.2 Recommendations

- i. Auditing firms in Delta State should invest in and expand the use of data analytics tools in audit engagements. These tools should be integrated into audit planning, risk assessment, and substantive testing processes to enhance audit efficiency, improve fraud detection, and strengthen audit quality.
- ii. Audit firms should adopt AI-driven audit applications such as automated transaction testing, anomaly detection systems, and continuous auditing platforms. Management should also ensure that AI systems are aligned with professional auditing standards to improve accuracy, objectivity, and reliability of audit outcomes.
- iii. Auditing firms should upgrade from traditional audit methods to advanced audit technologies such as computer-assisted audit techniques (CAATs), cloud-based audit platforms, and integrated audit management systems. This will improve audit documentation, compliance with auditing standards, and overall audit quality.

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